

Mobile Price With The Demand of The Mobile Phone Features Prediction using KNN

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Abstract

Over the last few decades, the mobile phone has shown good number of selling growth in comparison with the other years. In fact, the revelation of the technology and digitalization of the world people are bound to buy a mobile phone. Hence, the demand of the mobile is going to increase which will result the high price of mobile phones. A lot of mobile company selling their phone with a lot of technological feauters. However, mobile phone prices are also categorized by the mobile phone features. As a result, some time buyers don't understand which mobile phone with features is the best fit for them with their expected price range. The approach of this work is based on the data science algorithms. Our model is able to predict the mobile price with the demand of the mobile phone features. We used a relavent and filtered algorithmic rules that can analyse the mobile phone price with it's installed mobile phone feature. The resulting model was deployed and used as a mobile phone price prediction tool. The aim of the deployed application is to inform the mobile buyers about the mobile price range in advance to avoid the losses of money and fraudness of mobile company.

Index Terms: KNN, Data Mining, Prediction, SAS, R

1 Introduction

In this contemporary world, Price is one of the most important value for any kind of purchase. Nowadays people always try to buy best product with a cheap price. However, any item price depends on it quality, feature and performance. There are lot of things in this world to purchase. Likewise, mobile phone is one of them. Clients always try to find out a phone which has good quality, performance and a lot feature. Therefore, some time clients are very confused that which mobile phone is good to buy. On the other hand, they try to compare different company mobile phone which can fullfill their expected dependency and price. As a result, people serach a lot of products price before buy it and also they want best feature in it. However, they don't want to loss their money by buying with a high price where the mobile phone has a lot limited number of feature in it.

1.1 Aim and Objective of the task

The aim of this task is to help client or the people to find out the price range of their expected product. However, they can also find out the price range of their product with their expected feature, performance and quality. The main objective of this task is.

- Client can serve their selected dependencies for find out the price range.
- K-nearest neighbour classifier will help to find out the price range for the client.
- Checking the accuracy of the classifier of K-nearest neighbour for the mobile data.

2 Literature Review

Scholarpedia found that the classification is one of the most fundamental approach to do the classification study where there is little or prior knowledge about the data. However, k-nearest-neighbour classification was developed for the discriminant analysis. The

k-neasrest-neighbour classifier based on a formula called the Euclidean distance which is depend on the test sample and the traning sample [1]. Other researcher reasearched about the mobile phone price on different classification algorithm. Therefore, they used the algorithm for feature selection and parameter optimization. Most of the part of this research they tried to follow the process of Machine lerning way to determine the output. They focused to choose the right algorithm and methods so that they can get the good results. In this paper they worked on Random Forest Classifier, Logistic Regression Classifier, Decision Tree Classifier, Linear and K-nearest-neighbour Classifier. Finally they come to decision that the ANOVA f-test feature has the highest test accuracy compared to other models [2]. Moreover, another researchers in the year 2012 mentioned In their research they mentioned about the device sensors a lot. They worked with the GPS, vision, audio, light, temperature, direction and acceleration. However, they tried to find out the user prediction in which device the user basically used the most of the phone. As a result, they designed a algorithmic model with the help of k-nearest-neighbour. The approach of the method was human activity classification problem with the help of mobile device carried by the user. In that phonem they tried to find the magnitude of the accelerometer data to identify the general activites performed by the user [3].

3 Datasets

This datasert has 21 features and 2000 entries. However, The data details are given below [5]:

- battery_power: Total energy a battery can store in one time measured in mAh
- blue: Has bluetooth or not
- clock_speed: speed at which microprocessor executes instructions
- dual_sim: Has dual sim support or not
- fc: Front Camera mega pixels
- four_g: Has 4G or not
- int_memory: Internal Memory in Gigabytes

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- m_dep: Mobile Depth in cm
- mobile_wt: Weight of mobile phone
- n_cores: Number of cores of processor
- pc: Primary Camera mega pixels
- px_height: Pixel Resolution Height
- px_width: Pixel Resolution Width
- ram: Random Access Memory in Mega Byte
- sc_h: Screen Height of mobile in cm
- sc_w: Screen Width of mobile in cm
- talk_time: longest time that a single battery charge will last when you are
- three_g: Has 3G or not
- touch_screen: Has touch screen or not
- wifi: Has wifi or not
- price_range: This is the target variable with value of 0(low cost), 1(medium cost), 2(high cost) and 3(very high cost).

3.1 Explanation and preparation of datasets

Besically, the data is taken from the website called kaggle. Here we find out that the data is already organized. In this dataset, The researcher used the k-nearest neighbour algorithm to fullfill its research requirement. However, the most imporatatn thing of the k-nearest-neighbour algorithm implementation is to measure the Euclidean distance.

$$d(p, q) = \sqrt{(p_1 - q_1)^2 + (p_2 - q_2)^2 + \dots + (p_n - q_n)^2} \quad (1)$$

The formula of the Euclidean distance is given below [4]: However, The researcher tried to figure out that is there any null value or not. There are 21 column in this dataset so we have to check each column for find out the null value. Therefore, after checking each column the R code replied the value FALSE. As a result, we can say that there is no null value into this dataset. However, below excel file picture will give us a good idea about the data field(Figure 1).

Figure 1. Data Field Excel.

The details of the each header of the csv file was mentioned on the Datasets section. On the other hand, the data on the every column is numeric. There is no other problem to measure the euclidian distance.

4 Implementation

4.1 Data mining using SAS Enterprise Miner

In to the SAS miner, the data mining tools is made with a organized way. As a result. The researcher can do any kind of task within a simple steps. However, for this k nearest-neighbour task we have to follow below workflow :

- Create project and import dataset
- Selecting feature and doing partition data
- MBR Node from SEMMA panel
- Choosing KNN parameters
- Running and Visualizing the results

Figure 2. SAS diagram panel

After making the diagram panel(Figure 2), now we are ready to load our data into the project. Therefore, we have to look around the SEMMA panel from our SAS enterprise miner software. In to the SEMMA panel we will see the first button called Simple. After clicking that simple button, we will get the file import GUI on the top of the button. The below photo will show us where this button located(Figure 3).

Figure 3. SEMMA panel

However, now we have to drag and drop that button to the diagram panel. When we did that we will see a bigger button is visualized into the diagram.

Figure 4. visualized SEMMA

The above(Figure 4)picture showing how the File Input button GUI will look like into the SAS enterprise miner. Then we are ready to import our file from the local storage or from our pc(Figure 5).

When we will click that button we will see that the software will ask for the data from us(Figure 6).

However, the researcher added the mobile-data.csv file for the k-nearest-neighbor analysis.Here we can see that our data is loaded into the SAS miner system.(Figure 7).

Figure 5. File Input GUI

Figure 6. data import option

Figure 7. data added for analysis

After loading the data we have a power to select specific rows or columns of that dataset. For doing that we need to click the variable. The picture will show us where the variable is located is(Figure 8).

Figure 8. variable selection in SAS

If we click the variable we will see the total column we have on our loaded CSV file.

Figure 9. loaded csv interface

One of the most important things we need to do here, without it we can not get any result for our KNN work. We have to define a target variable here, the KNN will discover the result on the basis of that target variable. After selecting the variable, we need to press ok for our k-nearest-neighbour analysis. The researcher selected the RAM value for the target variable for his dataset (Figure 9).

However, we are ready for the data partitioning or the validating phase. Therefore, again we need to go to the SEMMA panel and select the simple section and then, we need to drag and drop the Data Partition to the diagram panel (Figure 10).

If we want to change the partition object such as training, validation and test. We can easily change that by selecting the Data Partition button.

The red mark showing that from where we can change those values from SAS enterprise miner. However, we didn't change any

Figure 10. Data Partition panel

Figure 11. Data Partition Objects

value because we want to do our analysis with the default value (Figure 11).

Now we will connect both node with each other by dragging the single line between them.

Figure 12. dragging single line in between

After dragging the line between them the diagram panel is look like the picture (Figure 12). So, our data selection and data partitioning section is done. Now we have to add another node called MBR. This node will help us to do the KNN task for our dataset.

The picture (Figure 13) showing us that we will find the MBR on the model button of the SEMMA panel. However, after finding that button, we need to drag and dropping that button to the diagram panel and then we have to connect the connector line with the Data Partition section (Figure 14).

The full meaning of the MBR is Memory-Based Reasoning node is a modelling tools that uses a k-nearest neighbour algorithm to categorize or predict observations (Figure 15).

Finally, all of the setting is done for the KNN process. Now we will run our total process form the diagram panel and then we are

Figure 13. MBR node

Figure 14. Data Partition connector

Figure 15. predict observations

going to describe all of the result output (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Run total process

Here we select the number of neighbors to 5 because we want to find 5 nearest value for our data. However, this means our analysis will work for k=5.

Figure 17. Run total process

After successfully, finish running of our program in SAS enterprise miner we can see that off the GUI button on the diagram panel is green (Figure 17). However, if we select the results button we will see all of the result for our k-nearest-neighbour algorithm for our target value will pop up in front of us.

Figure 18. KNN vs RAM

As we mentioned earlier, we are going to analysis our KNN with a target value called RAM. The output generated the value which is related to RAM on the dataset and also it gave us the value with matching number of neighbour we selected before running program (Figure 18).

4.2 Implementation in R

In this study, we use the R programming language to use the classification algorithm called K-nearest neighbour. Here some sample steps are followed to do the k-nearest neighbour.

4.2.1 Step 1 At first here we load the csv file to train our data. Into the csv file all of the dataset are stored into the Rstudio. After loading the data into Rstudio it showed us there was 2000 object and 21 variables (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Data loading code in R

4.2.2 Step 2 In this step the researcher tried to match the data with csv file that all of the things were ok on the Rstudio. Here after running the names function we found all of the column name of the csv file (Figure 20).

Figure 20. column names of data

4.2.3 Step 3 Checking the summary of the dataset. Summary function helped to find out all of the summary information about the dataset (Figure 21).

Figure 21. dataset summary information

4.2.4 Step 4 Checking is there any null value in any column or not. The below code help us to find out the null value into the dataset. Into the code the numbers were mentioning the column number. Into the dataset there were 21 column so we have to mention all of the column number to check each column (Figure 22).

After running the code the output showed us the following line on the console that was FALSE (Figure 23).

```
17 #checking is there any null value.
18 mobile_data_check_null1 <- mobile_data[,c(1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21)]
19 mobile_data_check_null1
20 is.null(mobile_data_check_null1)
21
```

Figure 22. null value check

```
> is.null(mobile_data_check_null1)
[1] FALSE
>
```

Figure 23. null value result

4.2.5 Step 5 In this step, we need to select our train column which we will match with the independent variable later. However, we should train the column data with the basis of independent variable. Here for the experiment, we will predict the phone price with the 5 type of column feature. Such as 1 = battery_power, 3 = clock_speed, 4 = dual_sim, 7 = internal_memory, 14 = ram, 21 = price_range. The price_range was our helping variable which would give us the decision of the mobile price and rest of the other was the requirement for the independent variable (Figure 24).

```
22 #selecting the train variable to find out the mobile phone price range
23 mobile_data_f <- mobile_data[,c(1,3,4,7,14,21)]
24 mobile_data_f
25
```

Figure 24. independent variable

4.2.6 Step 6 After selecting the train value we have to modify it to the Euclidean so that we can use it for the future step formula. Here the researcher stored the new data into new data variable called the 'mobile_data_f' (Figure 25).

```
26 #converting the data for euclidean distance measure
27 mobile_data_f$euclidean_distance
28 mobile_data_f
29
```

Figure 25. Euclidean formula

The console showed that the new dataset was ready for the further work which was holding the expected column that the researcher wanted (Figure 26).

```
> mobile_data_f
  battery_power clock_speed dual_sim int_memory ram price_range
1 842          2.2         0          7 2549         1
2 1021         0.5         1          53 2631         2
3 563          0.5         1          41 2603         2
4 615          2.5         0          10 2769         2
5 1821         1.2         0          44 1411         1
6 1859         0.5         1          22 1067         1
7 1821         1.7         0          10 3220         3
8 1954         0.5         1          24 700         0
9 1445         0.5         0          53 1099         0
10 509          0.6         1          9 513         0
11 769          2.9         1          9 3946         3
12 1520         2.2         0          33 3826         3
13 1115         2.8         0          33 1423         1
```

Figure 26. wanted information

4.2.7 Step 7 Assigning the independent variable which was needed by the client when they would buy the phone. Here each independent variable mentioned for each feature of the phone. The following code identified that the client want battery power 1536, clock speed of the phone should be 2.6, there should be one sim supported not the dual sim, the front camera 12 mega pixel and internal memory should be 30 gb and ram should be 2600 (Figure 27).

4.2.8 Step 8 Now the data is ready for the final important task to measure the Euclidean distance. The function for the distance measure is given (Figure 28).

```
30 #assigning the independent variable called the mobile feature categories
31 bat_power <- 1536
32 clo_speed <- 2.6
33 dual_sim <- 0
34 internal_memory <- 30
35 ram_power <- 2600
36
```

Figure 27. feature categories

```
41 # Calculating the Euclidean distances
42 for(i in 1:length)
43 {
44   mobile_data_f$euclidean_distance[i] = sqrt(
45     (mobile_data_f$battery_power[i]-bat_power)^2+
46     (mobile_data_f$clock_speed[i]-clo_speed)^2+
47     (mobile_data_f$dual_sim[i]-dual_sim)^2+
48     (mobile_data_f$int_memory[i]-internal_memory)^2+
49     (mobile_data_f$ram[i]-ram_power)^2
50   )
51 }
52
```

Figure 28. Before Euclidean distance measure

The formula did the calculation for the 5 types of category that we set before and done it's process without any error (Figure 29).

```
> # Calculating the Euclidean distances
> for(i in 1:length)
+ {
+   mobile_data_f$euclidean_distance[i] = sqrt(
+     (mobile_data_f$battery_power[i]-bat_power)^2+
+     (mobile_data_f$clock_speed[i]-clo_speed)^2+
+     (mobile_data_f$dual_sim[i]-dual_sim)^2+
+     (mobile_data_f$int_memory[i]-internal_memory)^2+
+     (mobile_data_f$ram[i]-ram_power)^2
+   )
+ }
>
```

Figure 29. After Euclidean measure

4.2.9 Step 9 In this step, we would see the dataset with the output of the Euclidean distance measured (Figure 30).

```
#output data set after doing the euclidean distance
mobile_data_f <- mobile_data_f[order(mobile_data_f$euclidean_distance),]
mobile_data_f
```

Figure 30. output data variable

The following code gave us the dataset with the value of Euclidean distance in a ordering format. We would see the output came from low to high into the Euclidean column (Figure 31).

```
> mobile_data_f
  battery_power clock_speed dual_sim int_memory ram price_range euclidean_distance
557 1552          1.2         0          53 2606         2         28.68728
449 1589          2.5         0          51 2612         2         58.25813
1202 1481          2.0         1          35 2835         2         85.39388
1204 1487          0.5         0          57 2963         2         87.10745
1388 1533          1.1         1          17 2520         2         81.12490
1133 1524          1.8         1          10 2678         2         81.42260
920 1521          2.0         0          60 2324         2         81.86183
352 1557          2.8         1          2 2690         3         96.57142
1034 1632          1.4         0          41 2614         2         97.64446
205 1472          2.3         0          61 2677         2         104.81455
224 1452          0.5         1          25 2669         2         108.84581
1940 1588          2.5         0          4 2506         2         110.52606
878 1444          0.6         0          48 2540         3         111.31936
1967 1583          1.2         1          14 2498         2         113.45466
1228 1426          2.5         0          55 2562         2         119.03365
789 1501          1.1         0          2 2487         2         121.57405
```

Figure 31. Euclidean distance column

4.2.10 Step 10 Assigning the k-nearest-neighbour measuring value. Here into the dataset the researcher took at least 5 neighbour value for fining the predication output (Figure 32).

```
56 # k nearest neighbor 5 values
57 k <- 5
58
59 mobile_data_f[1:k,]
60
61
```

Figure 32. Selecting neighbor 5

Finally the most nearest 5 values output would set into the dataset called 'mobile_data_f' (Figure 33). So here we can see the nearest value with the order sequence of Euclidean distance.

```
> # k nearest neighbor 5 values
> k <- 5
> mobile_data_f[1:k,]
  battery_power  clock_speed  dual_sim  int_memory  ram  price_range  euclidean_distance
557           1552           1.2         0           53  2606           2           28.68728
449           1589           2.5         0           51  2612           2           58.25813
1202          1481           2.0         1           35  2635           2           65.39388
1204          1487           0.5         0           37  2563           2           67.10745
1388          1533           1.1         1           17  2520           2           81.12490
```

Figure 33. most nearest 5 values output

4.2.11 Step 11 In this section, the dataset we used we categories the output into four ways Low, Medium, High and Very High.

```
63 cclass1 <- sum(mobile_data_f$price_range[1:k]==1)
64 cclass2 <- sum(mobile_data_f$price_range[1:k]==2)
65 cclass3 <- sum(mobile_data_f$price_range[1:k]==3)
66 if (cclass1 > k/2)
67 {
68   print("The query point belongs to Medium cost")
69 } else if (cclass2 > k/2)
70 {
71   print("The query point belongs to High cost")
72 } else if (cclass3 > k/2){
73   print("The query point belongs to Very High cost")
74 } else {
75   print("The query point belongs to Low Cost")
76 }
77
```

Figure 34. output categories

Every category we mentioned into four different class into the code. We measured the output value with a middle bordered value which was the identifier of the output (Figure 34).

```
> cclass1 <- sum(mobile_data_f$price_range[1:k]==1)
> cclass2 <- sum(mobile_data_f$price_range[1:k]==2)
> cclass3 <- sum(mobile_data_f$price_range[1:k]==3)
> if (cclass1 > k/2)
+ {
+   print("The query point belongs to Medium cost")
+ } else if (cclass2 > k/2)
+ {
+   print("The query point belongs to High cost")
+ } else if (cclass3 > k/2){
+   print("The query point belongs to Very High cost")
+ } else {
+   print("The query point belongs to Low Cost")
+ }
+ }
[1] "The query point belongs to High cost"
>
```

Figure 35. query point high cost

Finally, we reached to our decision point and k-nearest-neighbor algorithm predict our value for the experiment data. Here the experiment data output showed us that the required phone price will be high cost if we wanted to buy with its expected 5 feature (Figure 35).

5 Results Analysis and Discussion

SAS enterprise miner software produced the result for our dataset with k-nearest neighbour algorithm. However, it showed score distribution, score distribution matrix with ram because the researcher selected the target value as a ram. On the other hand, SAS software gave us the output in a fit statistics. On the score distribution train graph, we can see that mean prediction value and the mean target value fitted with each other. However, after 300 the mean target value crossed the mean prediction value.

On the other hand, Our R programming experiment result showed that the mobile price will be high cost price if anyone wanted to buy with the mentioned feature such as battery power, clock speed, dual sim, internal memory and ram. From the analysis, we can also see that the Euclidean distance is also measured on

the console of Rstudio. therefore, if we want to know the distance between the k and other values, we can get that idea easily. In this task, we mentioned k value = 5, that means we wanted to find out total 5 nearest neighbour value from our dataset for the specific mobile feature.

6 Conclusion

In conclusion, the researcher did the experiment with an algorithmic way and found out the expected output. The prediction done by the k-nearest-neighbour algorithm not only helping to take decision for the mobile phone buyer but also give them the clear idea about the budget range and mobile feature. However, the output totally depends on the dataset that means the more clean and accurate dataset will produce more accurate prediction. Finally, In a line, we can say that the k-nearest-neighbour algorithm is one of the best algorithmic method to find out prediction for any kind of research or experiment.

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